

Universal Magic Squares of Orders 128, 126 and 120 With Digits 1 and 8

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*The whole work is without use of any
programming language.*

Abstract

*This work brings magic squares of type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ using the digits 1 and 8. Each magic square contains 14-digits in each cell. Just with two digits, one can have exactly 16384 different possibilities of 14-digits combinations from two digits. In case of $4k$, we have written magic squares of orders, 4, 8, ..., 60, 64, ..., 124, 128. In case $6k$, we have written magic squares of orders 6, 12, ..., 54, 60, 120, 126. In case of $12k$, we have written magic squares of orders 6, 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 84, 96, 108 and 120. In each case, all the blocks of magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 12 are with **equal magic sums**. The same work for the digits 2 and 5 is done in Taneja [48], and for the digits 6 and 9 can be seen in Taneja [49]. The work on multiples of 3, 5, 7 etc. shall be done elsewhere. Later, the idea is to extend the same work up to magic square of order 256 having 16-digits in each cell just with two digits: $\{1, 8\}$, $\{2, 5\}$ and $\{6, 9\}$. In the first two cases, the work is always **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, while in the third case the work is only **upside-down**. When the magic squares are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, we call them as **universal magic squares**. The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just based on the number's combinations.*

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1 Introduction

In the previous papers [39, 40, 41], the author worked with three groups of numbers for the magic squares of orders 3 to 32. In [42, 43, 44], the author worked with three groups of numbers for the magic squares of orders 33 to 64. In the case, the work is only for the magic squares multiples of 4, 6 and 12. In each group there are only two digits, i.e., $\{1, 8\}$, $\{2, 5\}$ and $\{6, 9\}$. In the first and second cases, we have results as **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, while in the third case for the digits $\{6, 9\}$, the results are only **upside-down**. In the second group with the digits $\{2, 5\}$, the numbers 2 and 5 are written in digital form to have the conditions for **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. In the third case, 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6, when we make 180° rotation. For the magic squares of orders 3 to 16 [39], **palindromic-type magic squares** are also given.

The whole work is based on the combination of two digits. For example, 2-digits combinations of two letters a and b gives us 4 possibilities, i.e., aa, ab, ba, bb . In the similar way considering 3 by 3 combinations of two letters, there are 8 possibilities, i.e., $aaa, aab, aac, abb, acc, abc, bbb, ccc$. Complete details of these combinations are given in [39, 40, 41].

This work is for the magic squares of orders multiples of 4, 6 and 12, i.e., of type $4k$, $6k$ and $12k$ using

just two numbers 1 and 8. In case of multiple of 4, we have written magic squares of orders 4, 8, 12, ..., 60, 64, 68, ..., 120, 124, 128. In case of multiple of 6, we have written magic squares of orders 6, 12, 18, ..., 60, 66, ..., 120, 126. In case of multiple of 12, we have written magic squares of orders 12, 24, 36, 48, 60, 72, 84, 96, 108 and 120. These constructions are based on **equal sum** magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 12 in each case. In each cell there are 14-digits combinations of 1 and 8. These magic squares are **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, i.e., **universal magic squares**. In case of magic squares of multiples of 4 and 12, all the magic squares are **pandiagonal**. We observe that multiples of 12 are already presents in multiples of 4 and 6. The difference is that in case of multiples of 12, the sub-blocks are formed by **semi-magic** squares of order 3, with **different semi-magic sums** resulting in a **pandiagonal magic squares** of order 12 with **equal magic sums**. Similar kind of work for the digits 2 and 5, and 6 and 9 are given in another papers [48, 49]. The work for the multiples of 3, 5, 7, etc., and the **bimagic** cases for the multiples of order 8, 9, 16, etc. shall be dealt later on.

The whole work is without use of any **programming language**. It is just with number's combinations. The study of magic squares of orders 129 to 256 shall be given in another works.

1.1 Blocks of 4

Making 7-digits combinations, of two numbers, for example, 1 and 8, there are total 128 possibilities. Let's divided these 128 numbers by 4, we get total 32 groups of four each. See below these 32 groups written in two parts. These are written in such a way that the sum of each four is always same.

Table 1.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
1111181	1888818	1111188	1111811	1111818	1111881	1111888	1118118	1118181	1118188	1118811	1118818	1118881	1181118	1181181	1181188
8888818	8111181	8888811	8888188	8888181	8888118	8888111	8881881	8881818	8881811	8881188	8881181	8881118	8818881	8818818	8818811
1811111	1811118	1188888	1181111	1818888	1881111	1118888	1881888	1818111	1181888	1188111	1811888	1888111	1888188	1811811	1188188
8188888	8188881	8811111	8818888	8181111	8118888	8881111	8118111	8181888	8818111	8811888	8188111	8111888	8111811	8188188	8811811
19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998

Table 2.

17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32
1181818	1181881	1188118	1188181	1188818	1188881	1811818	1811881	1818118	1818881	1881118	1111111	1111118	1118111	1188811	1818181
8818181	8818118	8811881	8811818	8811181	8811118	8188181	8188118	8181881	8181118	8118881	8888888	8888881	8881888	8811188	8181818
1818188	1881811	1881188	1818811	1811188	1888811	1818818	1881181	1881818	1888181	1888118	1888881	1888888	1181811	1811181	1881881
8181811	8118188	8118811	8181188	8188811	8111188	8181181	8118818	8118181	8111818	8111881	8111118	8111111	8818188	8188818	8118118
19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998	19999998

The above groups are written in such a way that they are with their **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers. For example, let's consider the group $\{1181818, 8818181, 1818188, 8181811\}$. In this case the **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers of 1181818, 8818181 are 8181811 and 1818188 respectively. The same happens with all the 32 groups. Making combinations of 32 groups with each other, it lead us to 1024 possibilities with 16 members each. Below are 1024 **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with **equal sums** given by $S_{4 \times 4}^n := 1999999999999998, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 1024$. These magic square are given in section Appendix 5

The magic squares appearing in Appendix 5 are constructed and numbered according to following two tables:

Table 5.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1111181	1888818	1111818	1111881	1111888	1118118	1118181	1111188	1111811	1118188	1118811	1118818	1118881	1181118	1181181	1181188	1181818	1181881	1188118	1188181	1188818
8888818	8111181	8888181	8888118	8888111	8881881	8881818	8888811	8888188	8881811	8881188	8881181	8881118	8818881	8818818	8818811	8818181	8818118	8811881	8811818	8811181
1811111	1811118	1818888	1881111	1118888	1881888	1818111	1188888	1181111	1181888	1188111	1811888	1888111	1888188	1811811	1188188	1818188	1881811	1881188	1818811	1811188
8188888	8188881	8181111	8118888	8881111	8118111	8181888	8811111	8818888	8818111	8811888	8188111	8111888	8111811	8188188	8811811	8181811	8118188	8118811	8181188	8188811
1111111	1888881	1118111	1181811	1188811	1811181	1818181	1111118	1888888	1881118	1888118	1818881	1888181	1818118	1881818	1811881	1881181	1811818	1818818	1888811	1188881
8888888	8111118	8881888	8818188	8811188	8188818	8181818	8888881	8111111	8118881	8111881	8181118	8111818	8181881	8118181	8188118	8118818	8181818	8111188	8111188	8811118
29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997

● **Upside-down and Mirror Looking**

As in case of blocks of 4, each group is considered **upside-down** and **mirror looking** in each case. Here it is little different. The groups are made in such a way that all the 6 numbers lead us to same sum, where first four numbers are the as of group 4, i.e, they are **upside-down** and **mirror looking** in itself. Writing the last two numbers in each as **upside-down** and **mirror looking**, we have the following table:

Table 6.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1111181	1888818	1111818	1111881	1111888	1118118	1118181	1111188	1111811	1118188	1118811	1118818	1118881	1181118	1181181	1181188	1181818	1181881	1188118	1188181	1188818
8888818	8111181	8888181	8888118	8888111	8881881	8881818	8888811	8888188	8881811	8881188	8881181	8881118	8818881	8818818	8818811	8818181	8818118	8811881	8811818	8811181
1811111	1811118	1818888	1881111	1118888	1881888	1818111	1188888	1181111	1181888	1188111	1811888	1888111	1888188	1811811	1188188	1818188	1881811	1881188	1818811	1811188
8188888	8188881	8181111	8118888	8881111	8118111	8181888	8811111	8818888	8818111	8811888	8188111	8111888	8111811	8188188	8811811	8181811	8118188	8118811	8181188	8188811
1111111	1888881	1118111	1181811	1188811	1811181	1818181	8111111	8888881	8111881	8118881	1888181	1818881	8118181	8181881	1881181	1811881	8181818	8188181	1188881	1888811
8888888	8111118	8881888	8818188	8811188	8188818	8181818	1888888	1111118	1888118	1881118	8111818	8181118	1881818	1818118	8118818	8188118	1818818	1811818	8811118	8111188
29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997	29999997

Thus we observe the above table that even if the members are different from the original value, but the sum is same in both the cases. This means that in case of magic squares made from the above table are always **upside-down** and **mirror looking**. Making possible combinations, these 21 groups lead us to 441 magic square of order 6 with equal magic sums $S_{6 \times 6}^n := 2999999999997, n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 441$. These magic squares are given in Appendix 6. The magic squares appearing in Appendix 6 are numbered according to following table:

Table 8.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1111181	1111811	1111888	1118188	1118881	1181188	1188118	1188881	1818118	1111111
1111188	1111818	1118118	1118811	1181118	1181818	1188181	1811818	1818881	1111118
1188888	1111881	1118181	1118818	1181181	1181881	1188818	1811881	1881118	1118111
1811111	1181111	1118888	1181888	1811811	1188188	1811188	1818818	1881818	1181811
1811118	1818888	1818111	1188111	1888111	1818188	1818811	1881181	1888118	1888881
1888818	1881111	1881888	1811888	1888188	1881811	1881188	1888811	1888181	1888888
8111181	8118888	8118111	8188111	8111811	8118188	8118811	8111188	8111818	8111111
8188881	8181111	8181888	8811888	8111888	8181811	8181188	8118818	8111881	8111118
8188888	8818888	8881111	8818111	8188188	8811811	8188811	8181181	8118181	8818188
8811111	8888118	8881818	8881181	8818818	8818118	8811181	8188118	8118881	8881888
8888811	8888181	8881881	8881188	8818881	8818181	8811818	8188181	8181118	8888881
8888818	8888188	8888111	8881811	8881118	8818811	8811881	8811118	8181881	8888888
59999994	59999994	59999994	59999994	59999994	59999994	59999994	59999994	59999994	59999994

The above groups are considered in such a way that they are with their **upside-down** and **mirror looking** numbers. Making possible combinations, these 10 groups, it lead us to 100 magic squares of order 12 with equal **magic sum** $S_{12 \times 12}^n := 5999999999994, n = 1, 2, \dots, 100$. These magic squares are given in Appendix 7, and are numbered according to following Table:

Table 9.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1=(1,1)	11=(1,2)	21=(1,3)	31=(1,4)	41=(1,5)	51=(1,6)	61=(1,7)	71=(1,8)	81=(1,9)	91=(1,10)
2=(2,1)	12=(2,2)	22=(2,3)	32=(2,4)	42=(2,5)	52=(2,6)	62=(2,7)	72=(2,8)	82=(2,9)	92=(2,10)
3=(3,1)	13=(3,2)	23=(3,3)	33=(3,4)	43=(3,5)	53=(3,6)	63=(3,7)	73=(3,8)	83=(3,9)	93=(3,10)
4=(4,1)	14=(4,2)	24=(4,3)	34=(4,4)	44=(4,5)	54=(4,6)	64=(4,7)	74=(4,8)	84=(4,9)	94=(4,10)
5=(5,1)	15=(5,2)	25=(5,3)	35=(5,4)	45=(5,5)	55=(5,6)	65=(5,7)	75=(5,8)	85=(5,9)	95=(5,10)
6=(6,1)	16=(6,2)	26=(6,3)	36=(6,4)	46=(6,5)	56=(6,6)	66=(6,7)	76=(6,8)	86=(6,9)	96=(6,10)
7=(7,1)	17=(7,2)	27=(7,3)	37=(7,4)	47=(7,5)	57=(7,6)	67=(7,7)	77=(7,8)	87=(7,9)	97=(7,10)
8=(8,1)	18=(8,2)	28=(8,3)	38=(8,4)	48=(8,5)	58=(8,6)	68=(8,7)	78=(8,8)	88=(8,9)	98=(8,10)
9=(9,1)	19=(9,2)	29=(9,3)	39=(9,4)	49=(9,5)	59=(9,6)	69=(9,7)	79=(9,8)	89=(9,9)	99=(9,10)
10=(10,1)	20=(10,2)	30=(10,3)	40=(10,4)	50=(10,5)	60=(10,6)	70=(10,7)	80=(10,8)	90=(10,9)	100=(10,10)

The numbers appearing in magic squares of order 12 given in Appendix 7 are written according to above table.

2 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 128

Let's combing the two parts given in Tables 3 and 4, and writing in a simplified form as 32×32 , we get a **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 128.

Table 11. Below are magic sums of magic squares multiples of 4 up to orders 128.

$S_{4 \times 4} := 19999999999998 \times 1 = 19999999999998$	$S_{72 \times 72} := 19999999999998 \times 18 = 359999999999964$
$S_{8 \times 8} := 19999999999998 \times 2 = 39999999999996$	$S_{76 \times 76} := 19999999999998 \times 19 = 379999999999962$
$S_{12 \times 12} := 19999999999998 \times 3 = 59999999999994$	$S_{80 \times 80} := 19999999999998 \times 20 = 399999999999960$
$S_{16 \times 16} := 19999999999998 \times 4 = 79999999999992$	$S_{84 \times 84} := 19999999999998 \times 21 = 419999999999958$
$S_{20 \times 20} := 19999999999998 \times 5 = 99999999999990$	$S_{88 \times 88} := 19999999999998 \times 22 = 439999999999956$
$S_{24 \times 24} := 19999999999998 \times 6 = 119999999999988$	$S_{92 \times 92} := 19999999999998 \times 23 = 459999999999954$
$S_{28 \times 28} := 19999999999998 \times 7 = 139999999999986$	$S_{96 \times 96} := 19999999999998 \times 24 = 479999999999952$
$S_{32 \times 32} := 19999999999998 \times 8 = 159999999999984$	$S_{100 \times 100} := 19999999999998 \times 25 = 499999999999950$
$S_{36 \times 36} := 19999999999998 \times 9 = 179999999999982$	$S_{104 \times 104} := 19999999999998 \times 26 = 519999999999948$
$S_{40 \times 40} := 19999999999998 \times 10 = 199999999999980$	$S_{108 \times 108} := 19999999999998 \times 27 = 539999999999946$
$S_{44 \times 44} := 19999999999998 \times 11 = 219999999999978$	$S_{112 \times 112} := 19999999999998 \times 28 = 559999999999944$
$S_{48 \times 48} := 19999999999998 \times 12 = 239999999999976$	$S_{116 \times 116} := 19999999999998 \times 29 = 579999999999942$
$S_{52 \times 52} := 19999999999998 \times 13 = 259999999999974$	$S_{120 \times 120} := 19999999999998 \times 30 = 599999999999940$
$S_{56 \times 56} := 19999999999998 \times 14 = 279999999999972$	$S_{124 \times 124} := 19999999999998 \times 31 = 619999999999938$
$S_{60 \times 60} := 19999999999998 \times 15 = 299999999999970$	$S_{128 \times 128} := 19999999999998 \times 32 = 639999999999936$
$S_{64 \times 64} := 19999999999998 \times 16 = 319999999999968$	
$S_{68 \times 68} := 19999999999998 \times 17 = 339999999999966$	

2.1 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of Order 4

In this case we shall bring **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of all orders multiples of 4 up to order 124. **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 128 is already given in 10. The following procedure shall be used to write **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of multiples of 4.

2.1.3 Orders 32 and 36

According to Figure 1, the magic squares of orders 32 and 36 are given by

7.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232

8.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265

In this case, the magic squares of orders 32 and 36 are **universal pandiagonal** with magic sums: $S_{32 \times 32} = 1599999999999984$ and $S_{36 \times 36} = 1799999999999982$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.4 Orders 40 and 44

According to Figure 1, the magic squares of orders 40 and 44 are given by

9.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298

10.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331

In this case, the magic squares of orders 40 and 44 are **universal pandiagonal** with magic sums: $S_{40 \times 40} = 1999999999999980$ and $S_{44 \times 44} = 2199999999999978$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 199999999999998$.

2.1.5 Orders 48 and 52

According to Figure 1, the magic squares of orders 48 and 52 are given by

11.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364

12.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397

In this case, the magic squares of orders 48 and 52 are **universal pandiagonal** with magic sums: $S_{48 \times 48} = 2399999999999976$ and $S_{52 \times 52} = 2599999999999974$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 199999999999998$.

2.1.6 Orders 56 and 60

According to Figure 1, the magic squares of orders 56 and 60 are given by

13.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430

14.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463

In this case, the magic squares of orders 56 and 60 are **universal pandiagonal** with magic sums: $S_{56 \times 56} = 2799999999999972$ and $S_{60 \times 60} = 2999999999999970$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.7 Order 64

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 64 is given by

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496

In this case, the magic square of order 64 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{64 \times 64} = 3199999999999968$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 199999999999998$.

2.1.8 Order 68

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 68 is given by

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	
16.	9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	
17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	

In this case, the magic square of order 68 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{68 \times 68} = 33999999999999966$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.9 Order 72

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 72 is given by

17.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	545
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	546
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	547
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	548
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560
17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561
18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562

In this case, the magic square of order 72 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{72 \times 72} = 3599999999999964$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.10 Order 76

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 76 is given by

18.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	545	577
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	546	578
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	547	579
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	548	580
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549	581
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592
17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593
18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594
19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595

In this case, the magic square of order 76 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{76 \times 76} = 37999999999999962$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.11 Order 80

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 80 is given by

19.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	545	577	609
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	546	578	610
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	547	579	611
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	548	580	612
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549	581	613
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582	614
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624
17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625
18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626
19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627
20	52	84	116	148	180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628

In this case, the magic square of order 80 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{80 \times 80} = 3999999999999960$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 199999999999998$.

2.1.12 Order 84

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 84 is given by

	1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	545	577	609	641
	2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	546	578	610	642
	3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	547	579	611	643
	4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	548	580	612	644
	5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549	581	613	645
	6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582	614	646
	7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615	647
	8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648
	9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649
	10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650
20.	11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651
	12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652
	13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653
	14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654
	15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655
	16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656
	17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657
	18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658
	19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659
	20	52	84	116	148	180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660
	21	53	85	117	149	181	213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661

In this case, the magic square of order 84 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{84 \times 84} = 4199999999999958$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.13 Order 88

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 88 is given by

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	545	577	609	641	673
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	546	578	610	642	674
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	547	579	611	643	675
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	548	580	612	644	676
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549	581	613	645	677
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582	614	646	678
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615	647	679
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648	680
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688
17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689
18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690
19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691
20	52	84	116	148	180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692
21	53	85	117	149	181	213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693
22	54	86	118	150	182	214	246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694

In this case, the magic square of order 88 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{88 \times 88} = 4399999999999956$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.14 Order 92

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 92 is given by

	1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	545	577	609	641	673	705
	2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	546	578	610	642	674	706
	3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	547	579	611	643	675	707
	4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	548	580	612	644	676	708
	5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549	581	613	645	677	709
	6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582	614	646	678	710
	7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615	647	679	711
	8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648	680	712
	9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681	713
	10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714
	11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715
22.	12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716
	13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717
	14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718
	15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719
	16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720
	17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721
	18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722
	19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723
	20	52	84	116	148	180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724
	21	53	85	117	149	181	213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725
	22	54	86	118	150	182	214	246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726
	23	55	87	119	151	183	215	247	279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727

In this case, the magic square of order 92 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{92 \times 92} = 45999999999999954$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.1.15 Order 96

According to Figure 1, the magic square of order 96 is given by

23.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481	513	545	577	609	641	673	705	737
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482	514	546	578	610	642	674	706	738
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483	515	547	579	611	643	675	707	739
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484	516	548	580	612	644	676	708	740
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549	581	613	645	677	709	741
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582	614	646	678	710	742
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615	647	679	711	743
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648	680	712	744
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752
17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753
18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754
19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755
20	52	84	116	148	180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756
21	53	85	117	149	181	213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757
22	54	86	118	150	182	214	246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758
23	55	87	119	151	183	215	247	279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759
24	56	88	120	152	184	216	248	280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504	536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760

In this case, the magic square of order 96 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{96 \times 96} = 4799999999999952$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

- (i) 4 parts of order 64;
- (ii) 16 parts of order 32;
- (iii) 64 parts of order 16;
- (iv) 256 parts of order 8.

Let's work below with all these four ways separately.

2.2.1 Orders 64

Let's divide the Figure 2 in 4 equal parts, we get

1.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225	257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226	258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227	259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228	260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488
9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496

2.

513	545	577	609	641	673	705	737	769	801	833	865	897	929	961	993
514	546	578	610	642	674	706	738	770	802	834	866	898	930	962	994
515	547	579	611	643	675	707	739	771	803	835	867	899	931	963	995
516	548	580	612	644	676	708	740	772	804	836	868	900	932	964	996
517	549	581	613	645	677	709	741	773	805	837	869	901	933	965	997
518	550	582	614	646	678	710	742	774	806	838	870	902	934	966	998
519	551	583	615	647	679	711	743	775	807	839	871	903	935	967	999
520	552	584	616	648	680	712	744	776	808	840	872	904	936	968	1000
521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745	777	809	841	873	905	937	969	1001
522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746	778	810	842	874	906	938	970	1002
523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747	779	811	843	875	907	939	971	1003
524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748	780	812	844	876	908	940	972	1004
525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749	781	813	845	877	909	941	973	1005
526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750	782	814	846	878	910	942	974	1006
527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751	783	815	847	879	911	943	975	1007
528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752	784	816	848	880	912	944	976	1008

3.

17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497
18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498
19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499
20	52	84	116	148	180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500
21	53	85	117	149	181	213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501
22	54	86	118	150	182	214	246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502
23	55	87	119	151	183	215	247	279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503
24	56	88	120	152	184	216	248	280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504
25	57	89	121	153	185	217	249	281	313	345	377	409	441	473	505
26	58	90	122	154	186	218	250	282	314	346	378	410	442	474	506
27	59	91	123	155	187	219	251	283	315	347	379	411	443	475	507
28	60	92	124	156	188	220	252	284	316	348	380	412	444	476	508
29	61	93	125	157	189	221	253	285	317	349	381	413	445	477	509
30	62	94	126	158	190	222	254	286	318	350	382	414	446	478	510
31	63	95	127	159	191	223	255	287	319	351	383	415	447	479	511
32	64	96	128	160	192	224	256	288	320	352	384	416	448	480	512

4.

529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753	785	817	849	881	913	945	977	1009
530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754	786	818	850	882	914	946	978	1010
531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755	787	819	851	883	915	947	979	1011
532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756	788	820	852	884	916	948	980	1012
533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757	789	821	853	885	917	949	981	1013
534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758	790	822	854	886	918	950	982	1014
535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759	791	823	855	887	919	951	983	1015
536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760	792	824	856	888	920	952	984	1016
537	569	601	633	665	697	729	761	793	825	857	889	921	953	985	1017
538	570	602	634	666	698	730	762	794	826	858	890	922	954	986	1018
539	571	603	635	667	699	731	763	795	827	859	891	923	955	987	1019
540	572	604	636	668	700	732	764	796	828	860	892	924	956	988	1020
541	573	605	637	669	701	733	765	797	829	861	893	925	957	989	1021
542	574	606	638	670	702	734	766	798	830	862	894	926	958	990	1022
543	575	607	639	671	703	735	767	799	831	863	895	927	959	991	1023
544	576	608	640	672	704	736	768	800	832	864	896	928	960	992	1024

The above four magic squares of order 64 are **universal pandiagonal** and with **equal magic sums**:
 $S_{64 \times 64} := 31999999999999968$

2.2.2 Orders 32

Let's divide the Figure 2 in 16 equal parts, we get

1.

1	33	65	97	129	161	193	225
2	34	66	98	130	162	194	226
3	35	67	99	131	163	195	227
4	36	68	100	132	164	196	228
5	37	69	101	133	165	197	229
6	38	70	102	134	166	198	230
7	39	71	103	135	167	199	231
8	40	72	104	136	168	200	232

4.

769	801	833	865	897	929	961	993
770	802	834	866	898	930	962	994
771	803	835	867	899	931	963	995
772	804	836	868	900	932	964	996
773	805	837	869	901	933	965	997
774	806	838	870	902	934	966	998
775	807	839	871	903	935	967	999
776	808	840	872	904	936	968	1000

2.

257	289	321	353	385	417	449	481
258	290	322	354	386	418	450	482
259	291	323	355	387	419	451	483
260	292	324	356	388	420	452	484
261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485
262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486
263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487
264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488

5.

9	41	73	105	137	169	201	233
10	42	74	106	138	170	202	234
11	43	75	107	139	171	203	235
12	44	76	108	140	172	204	236
13	45	77	109	141	173	205	237
14	46	78	110	142	174	206	238
15	47	79	111	143	175	207	239
16	48	80	112	144	176	208	240

3.

513	545	577	609	641	673	705	737
514	546	578	610	642	674	706	738
515	547	579	611	643	675	707	739
516	548	580	612	644	676	708	740
517	549	581	613	645	677	709	741
518	550	582	614	646	678	710	742
519	551	583	615	647	679	711	743
520	552	584	616	648	680	712	744

6.

265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489
266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490
267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491
268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492
269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493
270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494
271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495
272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496

7.

521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745
522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746
523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747
524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748
525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749
526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750
527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751
528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752

10.

273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497
274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498
275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499
276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500
277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501
278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502
279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503
280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504

8.

777	809	841	873	905	937	969	1001
778	810	842	874	906	938	970	1002
779	811	843	875	907	939	971	1003
780	812	844	876	908	940	972	1004
781	813	845	877	909	941	973	1005
782	814	846	878	910	942	974	1006
783	815	847	879	911	943	975	1007
784	816	848	880	912	944	976	1008

11.

529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753
530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754
531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755
532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756
533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757
534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758
535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759
536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760

9.

17	49	81	113	145	177	209	241
18	50	82	114	146	178	210	242
19	51	83	115	147	179	211	243
20	52	84	116	148	180	212	244
21	53	85	117	149	181	213	245
22	54	86	118	150	182	214	246
23	55	87	119	151	183	215	247
24	56	88	120	152	184	216	248

12.

785	817	849	881	913	945	977	1009
786	818	850	882	914	946	978	1010
787	819	851	883	915	947	979	1011
788	820	852	884	916	948	980	1012
789	821	853	885	917	949	981	1013
790	822	854	886	918	950	982	1014
791	823	855	887	919	951	983	1015
792	824	856	888	920	952	984	1016

13.

25	57	89	121	153	185	217	249
26	58	90	122	154	186	218	250
27	59	91	123	155	187	219	251
28	60	92	124	156	188	220	252
29	61	93	125	157	189	221	253
30	62	94	126	158	190	222	254
31	63	95	127	159	191	223	255
32	64	96	128	160	192	224	256

15.

537	569	601	633	665	697	729	761
538	570	602	634	666	698	730	762
539	571	603	635	667	699	731	763
540	572	604	636	668	700	732	764
541	573	605	637	669	701	733	765
542	574	606	638	670	702	734	766
543	575	607	639	671	703	735	767
544	576	608	640	672	704	736	768

14.

281	313	345	377	409	441	473	505
282	314	346	378	410	442	474	506
283	315	347	379	411	443	475	507
284	316	348	380	412	444	476	508
285	317	349	381	413	445	477	509
286	318	350	382	414	446	478	510
287	319	351	383	415	447	479	511
288	320	352	384	416	448	480	512

16.

793	825	857	889	921	953	985	1017
794	826	858	890	922	954	986	1018
795	827	859	891	923	955	987	1019
796	828	860	892	924	956	988	1020
797	829	861	893	925	957	989	1021
798	830	862	894	926	958	990	1022
799	831	863	895	927	959	991	1023
800	832	864	896	928	960	992	1024

The above 16 magic squares of order 32 are **universal pandiagonal** with **equal magic sums**: $S_{32 \times 32} := 15999999999999984$

2.2.3 Orders 16

Let's divide the Figure 2 in 64 equal parts, we get

1.

1	33	65	97
2	34	66	98
3	35	67	99
4	36	68	100

2.

5	37	69	101
6	38	70	102
7	39	71	103
8	40	72	104

3.

9	41	73	105
10	42	74	106
11	43	75	107
12	44	76	108

4.

13	45	77	109
14	46	78	110
15	47	79	111
16	48	80	112

5.

17	49	81	113
18	50	82	114
19	51	83	115
20	52	84	116

11.

137	169	201	233
138	170	202	234
139	171	203	235
140	172	204	236

17.

257	289	321	353
258	290	322	354
259	291	323	355
260	292	324	356

23.

281	313	345	377
282	314	346	378
283	315	347	379
284	316	348	380

6.

21	53	85	117
22	54	86	118
23	55	87	119
24	56	88	120

12.

141	173	205	237
142	174	206	238
143	175	207	239
144	176	208	240

18.

261	293	325	357
262	294	326	358
263	295	327	359
264	296	328	360

24.

285	317	349	381
286	318	350	382
287	319	351	383
288	320	352	384

7.

25	57	89	121
26	58	90	122
27	59	91	123
28	60	92	124

13.

145	177	209	241
146	178	210	242
147	179	211	243
148	180	212	244

19.

265	297	329	361
266	298	330	362
267	299	331	363
268	300	332	364

25.

385	417	449	481
386	418	450	482
387	419	451	483
388	420	452	484

8.

29	61	93	125
30	62	94	126
31	63	95	127
32	64	96	128

14.

149	181	213	245
150	182	214	246
151	183	215	247
152	184	216	248

20.

269	301	333	365
270	302	334	366
271	303	335	367
272	304	336	368

26.

389	421	453	485
390	422	454	486
391	423	455	487
392	424	456	488

9.

129	161	193	225
130	162	194	226
131	163	195	227
132	164	196	228

15.

153	185	217	249
154	186	218	250
155	187	219	251
156	188	220	252

21.

273	305	337	369
274	306	338	370
275	307	339	371
276	308	340	372

27.

393	425	457	489
394	426	458	490
395	427	459	491
396	428	460	492

10.

133	165	197	229
134	166	198	230
135	167	199	231
136	168	200	232

16.

157	189	221	253
158	190	222	254
159	191	223	255
160	192	224	256

22.

277	309	341	373
278	310	342	374
279	311	343	375
280	312	344	376

28.

397	429	461	493
398	430	462	494
399	431	463	495
400	432	464	496

29.

401	433	465	497
402	434	466	498
403	435	467	499
404	436	468	500

35.

521	553	585	617
522	554	586	618
523	555	587	619
524	556	588	620

41.

641	673	705	737
642	674	706	738
643	675	707	739
644	676	708	740

47.

665	697	729	761
666	698	730	762
667	699	731	763
668	700	732	764

30.

405	437	469	501
406	438	470	502
407	439	471	503
408	440	472	504

36.

525	557	589	621
526	558	590	622
527	559	591	623
528	560	592	624

42.

645	677	709	741
646	678	710	742
647	679	711	743
648	680	712	744

48.

669	701	733	765
670	702	734	766
671	703	735	767
672	704	736	768

31.

409	441	473	505
410	442	474	506
411	443	475	507
412	444	476	508

37.

529	561	593	625
530	562	594	626
531	563	595	627
532	564	596	628

43.

649	681	713	745
650	682	714	746
651	683	715	747
652	684	716	748

49.

769	801	833	865
770	802	834	866
771	803	835	867
772	804	836	868

32.

413	445	477	509
414	446	478	510
415	447	479	511
416	448	480	512

38.

533	565	597	629
534	566	598	630
535	567	599	631
536	568	600	632

44.

653	685	717	749
654	686	718	750
655	687	719	751
656	688	720	752

50.

773	805	837	869
774	806	838	870
775	807	839	871
776	808	840	872

33.

513	545	577	609
514	546	578	610
515	547	579	611
516	548	580	612

39.

537	569	601	633
538	570	602	634
539	571	603	635
540	572	604	636

45.

657	689	721	753
658	690	722	754
659	691	723	755
660	692	724	756

51.

777	809	841	873
778	810	842	874
779	811	843	875
780	812	844	876

34.

517	549	581	613
518	550	582	614
519	551	583	615
520	552	584	616

40.

541	573	605	637
542	574	606	638
543	575	607	639
544	576	608	640

46.

661	693	725	757
662	694	726	758
663	695	727	759
664	696	728	760

52.

781	813	845	877
782	814	846	878
783	815	847	879
784	816	848	880

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{16 \times 16} = 7999999999999992$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$.

2.2.4 Orders 8

Let's divide the Figure 2 in 256 equal parts, we get

1. <table border="1"><tr><td>1</td><td>33</td></tr><tr><td>2</td><td>34</td></tr></table>	1	33	2	34	11. <table border="1"><tr><td>21</td><td>53</td></tr><tr><td>22</td><td>54</td></tr></table>	21	53	22	54	21. <table border="1"><tr><td>73</td><td>105</td></tr><tr><td>74</td><td>106</td></tr></table>	73	105	74	106	31. <table border="1"><tr><td>93</td><td>125</td></tr><tr><td>94</td><td>126</td></tr></table>	93	125	94	126	41. <table border="1"><tr><td>145</td><td>177</td></tr><tr><td>146</td><td>178</td></tr></table>	145	177	146	178	51. <table border="1"><tr><td>197</td><td>229</td></tr><tr><td>198</td><td>230</td></tr></table>	197	229	198	230	61. <table border="1"><tr><td>217</td><td>249</td></tr><tr><td>218</td><td>250</td></tr></table>	217	249	218	250	71. <table border="1"><tr><td>269</td><td>301</td></tr><tr><td>270</td><td>302</td></tr></table>	269	301	270	302
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180.	<table border="1"><tr><td>711</td><td>743</td></tr><tr><td>712</td><td>744</td></tr></table>	711	743	712	744	190.	<table border="1"><tr><td>731</td><td>763</td></tr><tr><td>732</td><td>764</td></tr></table>	731	763	732	764	200.	<table border="1"><tr><td>783</td><td>815</td></tr><tr><td>784</td><td>816</td></tr></table>	783	815	784	816	210.	<table border="1"><tr><td>835</td><td>867</td></tr><tr><td>836</td><td>868</td></tr></table>	835	867	836	868	220.	<table border="1"><tr><td>855</td><td>887</td></tr><tr><td>856</td><td>888</td></tr></table>	855	887	856	888	230.	<table border="1"><tr><td>907</td><td>939</td></tr><tr><td>908</td><td>940</td></tr></table>	907	939	908	940	240.	<table border="1"><tr><td>927</td><td>959</td></tr><tr><td>928</td><td>960</td></tr></table>	927	959	928	960	250.	<table border="1"><tr><td>979</td><td>1011</td></tr><tr><td>980</td><td>1012</td></tr></table>	979	1011	980	1012
711	743																																														
712	744																																														
731	763																																														
732	764																																														
783	815																																														
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855	887																																														
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928	960																																														
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980	1012																																														
181.	<table border="1"><tr><td>713</td><td>745</td></tr><tr><td>714</td><td>746</td></tr></table>	713	745	714	746	191.	<table border="1"><tr><td>733</td><td>765</td></tr><tr><td>734</td><td>766</td></tr></table>	733	765	734	766	201.	<table border="1"><tr><td>785</td><td>817</td></tr><tr><td>786</td><td>818</td></tr></table>	785	817	786	818	211.	<table border="1"><tr><td>837</td><td>869</td></tr><tr><td>838</td><td>870</td></tr></table>	837	869	838	870	221.	<table border="1"><tr><td>857</td><td>889</td></tr><tr><td>858</td><td>890</td></tr></table>	857	889	858	890	231.	<table border="1"><tr><td>909</td><td>941</td></tr><tr><td>910</td><td>942</td></tr></table>	909	941	910	942	241.	<table border="1"><tr><td>961</td><td>993</td></tr><tr><td>962</td><td>994</td></tr></table>	961	993	962	994	251.	<table border="1"><tr><td>981</td><td>1013</td></tr><tr><td>982</td><td>1014</td></tr></table>	981	1013	982	1014
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982	1014																																														
182.	<table border="1"><tr><td>715</td><td>747</td></tr><tr><td>716</td><td>748</td></tr></table>	715	747	716	748	192.	<table border="1"><tr><td>735</td><td>767</td></tr><tr><td>736</td><td>768</td></tr></table>	735	767	736	768	202.	<table border="1"><tr><td>787</td><td>819</td></tr><tr><td>788</td><td>820</td></tr></table>	787	819	788	820	212.	<table border="1"><tr><td>839</td><td>871</td></tr><tr><td>840</td><td>872</td></tr></table>	839	871	840	872	222.	<table border="1"><tr><td>859</td><td>891</td></tr><tr><td>860</td><td>892</td></tr></table>	859	891	860	892	232.	<table border="1"><tr><td>911</td><td>943</td></tr><tr><td>912</td><td>944</td></tr></table>	911	943	912	944	242.	<table border="1"><tr><td>963</td><td>995</td></tr><tr><td>964</td><td>996</td></tr></table>	963	995	964	996	252.	<table border="1"><tr><td>983</td><td>1015</td></tr><tr><td>984</td><td>1016</td></tr></table>	983	1015	984	1016
715	747																																														
716	748																																														
735	767																																														
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984	1016																																														
183.	<table border="1"><tr><td>717</td><td>749</td></tr><tr><td>718</td><td>750</td></tr></table>	717	749	718	750	193.	<table border="1"><tr><td>769</td><td>801</td></tr><tr><td>770</td><td>802</td></tr></table>	769	801	770	802	203.	<table border="1"><tr><td>789</td><td>821</td></tr><tr><td>790</td><td>822</td></tr></table>	789	821	790	822	213.	<table border="1"><tr><td>841</td><td>873</td></tr><tr><td>842</td><td>874</td></tr></table>	841	873	842	874	223.	<table border="1"><tr><td>861</td><td>893</td></tr><tr><td>862</td><td>894</td></tr></table>	861	893	862	894	233.	<table border="1"><tr><td>913</td><td>945</td></tr><tr><td>914</td><td>946</td></tr></table>	913	945	914	946	243.	<table border="1"><tr><td>965</td><td>997</td></tr><tr><td>966</td><td>998</td></tr></table>	965	997	966	998	253.	<table border="1"><tr><td>985</td><td>1017</td></tr><tr><td>986</td><td>1018</td></tr></table>	985	1017	986	1018
717	749																																														
718	750																																														
769	801																																														
770	802																																														
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986	1018																																														
184.	<table border="1"><tr><td>719</td><td>751</td></tr><tr><td>720</td><td>752</td></tr></table>	719	751	720	752	194.	<table border="1"><tr><td>771</td><td>803</td></tr><tr><td>772</td><td>804</td></tr></table>	771	803	772	804	204.	<table border="1"><tr><td>791</td><td>823</td></tr><tr><td>792</td><td>824</td></tr></table>	791	823	792	824	214.	<table border="1"><tr><td>843</td><td>875</td></tr><tr><td>844</td><td>876</td></tr></table>	843	875	844	876	224.	<table border="1"><tr><td>863</td><td>895</td></tr><tr><td>864</td><td>896</td></tr></table>	863	895	864	896	234.	<table border="1"><tr><td>915</td><td>947</td></tr><tr><td>916</td><td>948</td></tr></table>	915	947	916	948	244.	<table border="1"><tr><td>967</td><td>999</td></tr><tr><td>968</td><td>1000</td></tr></table>	967	999	968	1000	254.	<table border="1"><tr><td>987</td><td>1019</td></tr><tr><td>988</td><td>1020</td></tr></table>	987	1019	988	1020
719	751																																														
720	752																																														
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772	804																																														
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988	1020																																														
185.	<table border="1"><tr><td>721</td><td>753</td></tr><tr><td>722</td><td>754</td></tr></table>	721	753	722	754	195.	<table border="1"><tr><td>773</td><td>805</td></tr><tr><td>774</td><td>806</td></tr></table>	773	805	774	806	205.	<table border="1"><tr><td>793</td><td>825</td></tr><tr><td>794</td><td>826</td></tr></table>	793	825	794	826	215.	<table border="1"><tr><td>845</td><td>877</td></tr><tr><td>846</td><td>878</td></tr></table>	845	877	846	878	225.	<table border="1"><tr><td>897</td><td>929</td></tr><tr><td>898</td><td>930</td></tr></table>	897	929	898	930	235.	<table border="1"><tr><td>917</td><td>949</td></tr><tr><td>918</td><td>950</td></tr></table>	917	949	918	950	245.	<table border="1"><tr><td>969</td><td>1001</td></tr><tr><td>970</td><td>1002</td></tr></table>	969	1001	970	1002	255.	<table border="1"><tr><td>989</td><td>1021</td></tr><tr><td>990</td><td>1022</td></tr></table>	989	1021	990	1022
721	753																																														
722	754																																														
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990	1022																																														
186.	<table border="1"><tr><td>723</td><td>755</td></tr><tr><td>724</td><td>756</td></tr></table>	723	755	724	756	196.	<table border="1"><tr><td>775</td><td>807</td></tr><tr><td>776</td><td>808</td></tr></table>	775	807	776	808	206.	<table border="1"><tr><td>795</td><td>827</td></tr><tr><td>796</td><td>828</td></tr></table>	795	827	796	828	216.	<table border="1"><tr><td>847</td><td>879</td></tr><tr><td>848</td><td>880</td></tr></table>	847	879	848	880	226.	<table border="1"><tr><td>899</td><td>931</td></tr><tr><td>900</td><td>932</td></tr></table>	899	931	900	932	236.	<table border="1"><tr><td>919</td><td>951</td></tr><tr><td>920</td><td>952</td></tr></table>	919	951	920	952	246.	<table border="1"><tr><td>971</td><td>1003</td></tr><tr><td>972</td><td>1004</td></tr></table>	971	1003	972	1004	256.	<table border="1"><tr><td>991</td><td>1023</td></tr><tr><td>992</td><td>1024</td></tr></table>	991	1023	992	1024
723	755																																														
724	756																																														
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920	952																																														
971	1003																																														
972	1004																																														
991	1023																																														
992	1024																																														

The above 256 magic squares of order 8 are **universal pandiagonal with equal magic sums: $S_{8 \times 8} := 3999999999999996$**

Let's see an example No. 239 in details as below:

Example 5. *A universal pandiagonal magic square of order 8 appearing in 239 is given by*

		399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996
	1888888111111	8111118888881	1111181111118	888881888888	1181818111111	8818188888881	1118111111118	8881888188888	399999999999996
399999999999996	1111181888888	8888811111118	1888888888881	8111118111111	1118111888888	8881888111118	1181818888881	8818188811111	399999999999996
399999999999996	8888818888881	1111188111111	811111888888	1888881111118	8881888888881	1118118111111	8818188188888	1181811111118	399999999999996
399999999999996	8111111111118	1888881888888	8888818111111	1111188888881	8818188111118	1181811888888	8881888111111	1118118888881	399999999999996
399999999999996	188888818188	8111118881888	1111181181811	888881181811	1181818818188	8818188881888	1118111181811	8881888181811	399999999999996
399999999999996	1111181181811	8888811181811	1888888881888	8111118818188	1118111181811	8881888118111	1181818881888	8818188881818	399999999999996
399999999999996	8888818881888	1111188818188	811111181811	188888118111	8881888881888	1118118818188	8818188181811	1181811181811	399999999999996
399999999999996	8111111181811	1888881181811	8888818818188	1111188881888	8818188118111	1181811181811	8881888818188	1118118881888	399999999999996
	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996	399999999999996

2.3 Magic Squares Multiples of 8

Below are different ways of writing **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of orders multiples of 8. Even though these are already appearing in subsections 2.1 and 2.2, but here these are calculated in a different way. See the Figure below:

already given in 10.

2.3.1 Orders 8, 16 and 24

According to Figure 3, the magic squares of orders 8, 16 and 24 are given by

1.

496	528
497	529

2.

463	495	527	559
464	496	528	560
465	497	529	561
466	498	530	562

3.

430	462	494	526	558	590
431	463	495	527	559	591
432	464	496	528	560	592
433	465	497	529	561	593
434	466	498	530	562	594
435	467	499	531	563	595

In this case, the magic squares of orders 8, 16 and 24 are **universal pandiagonal** with magic sums: $S_{8 \times 8} = 3999999999999996$, $S_{16 \times 16} = 7999999999999992$ and $S_{24 \times 24} = 1199999999999998$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$

2.3.2 Orders 32 and 40

According to Figure 3, the magic squares of orders 32 and 40 are given by

4.

397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621
398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622
399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623
400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624
401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625
402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626
403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627
404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628

5.

364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652
365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653
366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654
367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655
368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656
369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657
370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658
371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659
372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660
373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661

In this case, the magic squares of orders 32 and 40 are **universal pandiagonal** with magic sums: $S_{32 \times 32} = 1599999999999984$ and $S_{40 \times 40} = 1999999999999980$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 199999999999998$

2.3.3 Orders 48 and 56

According to Figure 3, the magic squares of orders 48 and 56 are given by

6.

331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683
332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684
333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685
334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686
335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687
336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688
337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689
338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690
339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691
340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692
341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693
342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694

7.

298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714
299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715
300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716
301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717
302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718
303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719
304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720
305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721
306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722
307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723
308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724
309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725
310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726
311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727

In this case, the magic squares of orders 48 and 56 are **universal pandiagonal** with magic sums: $S_{48 \times 48} = 2399999999999976$ and $S_{56 \times 56} = 2799999999999972$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 199999999999998$

2.3.4 Order 64

According to Figure 3, the magic square of order 64 is given by

8.

265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745
266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746
267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747
268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748
269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749
270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750
271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751
272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752
273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753
274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754
275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755
276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756
277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757
278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758
279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759
280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504	536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760

In this case, the magic square of order 64 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{64 \times 64} = 3199999999999968$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 199999999999998$

2.3.5 Order 72

According to Figure 3, the magic square of order 72 is given by

9.

232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648	680	712	744	776
233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745	777
234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746	778
235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747	779
236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748	780
237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749	781
238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750	782
239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751	783
240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752	784
241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753	785
242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754	786
243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755	787
244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756	788
245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757	789
246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758	790
247	279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759	791
248	280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504	536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760	792
249	281	313	345	377	409	441	473	505	537	569	601	633	665	697	729	761	793

In this case, the magic square of order 72 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{72 \times 72} = 35999999999999964$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$

2.3.6 Order 80

According to Figure 3, the magic square of order 80 is given by

10.

199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615	647	679	711	743	775	807
200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648	680	712	744	776	808
201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745	777	809
202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746	778	810
203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747	779	811
204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748	780	812
205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749	781	813
206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750	782	814
207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751	783	815
208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752	784	816
209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753	785	817
210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754	786	818
211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755	787	819
212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756	788	820
213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757	789	821
214	246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758	790	822
215	247	279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759	791	823
216	248	280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504	536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760	792	824
217	249	281	313	345	377	409	441	473	505	537	569	601	633	665	697	729	761	793	825
218	250	282	314	346	378	410	442	474	506	538	570	602	634	666	698	730	762	794	826

In this case, the magic square of order 80 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{80 \times 80} = 3999999999999960$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$

2.3.7 Order 88

According to Figure 3, the magic square of order 88 is given by

166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582	614	646	678	710	742	774	806	838
167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615	647	679	711	743	775	807	839
168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648	680	712	744	776	808	840
169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745	777	809	841
170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746	778	810	842
171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747	779	811	843
172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748	780	812	844
173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749	781	813	845
174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750	782	814	846
175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751	783	815	847
176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752	784	816	848
177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753	785	817	849
178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754	786	818	850
179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755	787	819	851
180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756	788	820	852
181	213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757	789	821	853
182	214	246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758	790	822	854
183	215	247	279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759	791	823	855
184	216	248	280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504	536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760	792	824	856
185	217	249	281	313	345	377	409	441	473	505	537	569	601	633	665	697	729	761	793	825	857
186	218	250	282	314	346	378	410	442	474	506	538	570	602	634	666	698	730	762	794	826	858
187	219	251	283	315	347	379	411	443	475	507	539	571	603	635	667	699	731	763	795	827	859

In this case, the magic square of order 88 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{88 \times 88} = 4399999999999956$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$

2.3.8 Order 96

According to Figure 3, the magic square of order 96 is given by

133	165	197	229	261	293	325	357	389	421	453	485	517	549	581	613	645	677	709	741	773	805	837	869
134	166	198	230	262	294	326	358	390	422	454	486	518	550	582	614	646	678	710	742	774	806	838	870
135	167	199	231	263	295	327	359	391	423	455	487	519	551	583	615	647	679	711	743	775	807	839	871
136	168	200	232	264	296	328	360	392	424	456	488	520	552	584	616	648	680	712	744	776	808	840	872
137	169	201	233	265	297	329	361	393	425	457	489	521	553	585	617	649	681	713	745	777	809	841	873
138	170	202	234	266	298	330	362	394	426	458	490	522	554	586	618	650	682	714	746	778	810	842	874
139	171	203	235	267	299	331	363	395	427	459	491	523	555	587	619	651	683	715	747	779	811	843	875
140	172	204	236	268	300	332	364	396	428	460	492	524	556	588	620	652	684	716	748	780	812	844	876
141	173	205	237	269	301	333	365	397	429	461	493	525	557	589	621	653	685	717	749	781	813	845	877
142	174	206	238	270	302	334	366	398	430	462	494	526	558	590	622	654	686	718	750	782	814	846	878
143	175	207	239	271	303	335	367	399	431	463	495	527	559	591	623	655	687	719	751	783	815	847	879
144	176	208	240	272	304	336	368	400	432	464	496	528	560	592	624	656	688	720	752	784	816	848	880
145	177	209	241	273	305	337	369	401	433	465	497	529	561	593	625	657	689	721	753	785	817	849	881
146	178	210	242	274	306	338	370	402	434	466	498	530	562	594	626	658	690	722	754	786	818	850	882
147	179	211	243	275	307	339	371	403	435	467	499	531	563	595	627	659	691	723	755	787	819	851	883
148	180	212	244	276	308	340	372	404	436	468	500	532	564	596	628	660	692	724	756	788	820	852	884
149	181	213	245	277	309	341	373	405	437	469	501	533	565	597	629	661	693	725	757	789	821	853	885
150	182	214	246	278	310	342	374	406	438	470	502	534	566	598	630	662	694	726	758	790	822	854	886
151	183	215	247	279	311	343	375	407	439	471	503	535	567	599	631	663	695	727	759	791	823	855	887
152	184	216	248	280	312	344	376	408	440	472	504	536	568	600	632	664	696	728	760	792	824	856	888
153	185	217	249	281	313	345	377	409	441	473	505	537	569	601	633	665	697	729	761	793	825	857	889
154	186	218	250	282	314	346	378	410	442	474	506	538	570	602	634	666	698	730	762	794	826	858	890
155	187	219	251	283	315	347	379	411	443	475	507	539	571	603	635	667	699	731	763	795	827	859	891
156	188	220	252	284	316	348	380	412	444	476	508	540	572	604	636	668	700	732	764	796	828	860	892

In this case, the magic square of order 96 is **universal pandiagonal** with magic sum: $S_{96 \times 96} = 4799999999999952$. All the 4×4 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 1999999999999998$

Table 12.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316	337	358	379	400	421
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317	338	359	380	401	422
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318	339	360	381	402	423
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319	340	361	382	403	424
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320	341	362	383	404	425
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321	342	363	384	405	426
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322	343	364	385	406	427
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323	344	365	386	407	428
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324	345	366	387	408	429
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325	346	367	388	409	430
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326	347	368	389	410	431
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327	348	369	390	411	432
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328	349	370	391	412	433
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329	350	371	392	413	434
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330	351	372	393	414	435
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331	352	373	394	415	436
17	38	59	80	101	122	143	164	185	206	227	248	269	290	311	332	353	374	395	416	437
18	39	60	81	102	123	144	165	186	207	228	249	270	291	312	333	354	375	396	417	438
19	40	61	82	103	124	145	166	187	208	229	250	271	292	313	334	355	376	397	418	439
20	41	62	83	104	125	146	167	188	209	230	251	272	293	314	335	356	377	398	419	440
21	42	63	84	105	126	147	168	189	210	231	252	273	294	315	336	357	378	399	420	441

The each number appearing in above table represents a **universal** magic square of order 6. The above Table 12 represents **universal** magic square of order 126 with **magic sum**: $S_{126 \times 126} := 6399999999999940$. Each number represent magic square of order 6 with equal **magic sums**: $S_{6 \times 6} := 2999999999999997$. These magic squares of order 6 are given in Appendix 6. Below are the magic sums of magic squares multiples of 6.

Table 13. Below are magic sums of magic squares multiples of 6 up to order 126.

3.1.1 Orders 12, 18, 24 and 30

According to Figure 4, the squares of orders 12, 18, 24 and 30 are given by

1.

1	22
2	23

2.

1	22	43
2	23	44
3	24	45

3.

1	22	43	64
2	23	44	65
3	24	45	66
4	25	46	67

4.

1	22	43	64	85
2	23	44	65	86
3	24	45	66	87
4	25	46	67	88
5	26	47	68	89

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{12 \times 12} := 599999999999994$, $S_{18 \times 18} := 899999999999991$, $S_{24 \times 24} := 1199999999999988$ and $S_{30 \times 30} := 1499999999999985$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 299999999999997$.

3.1.2 Orders 36 and 42

According to Figure 4, the squares of orders 36 and 42 are given by

5.

1	22	43	64	85	106
2	23	44	65	86	107
3	24	45	66	87	108
4	25	46	67	88	109
5	26	47	68	89	110
6	27	48	69	90	111

6.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127
2	23	44	65	86	107	128
3	24	45	66	87	108	129
4	25	46	67	88	109	130
5	26	47	68	89	110	131
6	27	48	69	90	111	132
7	28	49	70	91	112	133

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{36 \times 36} := 1799999999999982$ and $S_{42 \times 42} := 2099999999999979$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 299999999999997$.

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{60 \times 60} := 2999999999999970$ and $S_{66 \times 66} := 3299999999999967$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 299999999999997$.

3.1.5 Orders 72 and 78

According to Figure 4, the squares of orders 72 and 78 are given by

11.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243

12.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{72 \times 72} := 3599999999999964$ and $S_{78 \times 78} := 3899999999999961$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 299999999999997$.

3.1.6 Order 84

According to Figure 4, the squares of order 84 is given by

13.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{84 \times 84} := 4199999999999958$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 2999999999999997$.

3.1.7 Order 90

According to Figure 4, the squares of order 90 is given by

14.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{90 \times 90} := 4499999999999955$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 2999999999999997$.

3.1.8 Order 96

According to Figure 4, the squares of order 96 is given by

15.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{96 \times 96} := 4799999999999952$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 2999999999999997$.

3.1.9 Order 102

According to Figure 4, the squares of order 102 is given by

16.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316	337
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317	338
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318	339
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319	340
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320	341
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321	342
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322	343
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323	344
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324	345
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325	346
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326	347
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327	348
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328	349
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329	350
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330	351
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331	352
17	38	59	80	101	122	143	164	185	206	227	248	269	290	311	332	353

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{102 \times 102} := 50999999999999949$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 2999999999999997$.

3.1.10 Order 108

According to Figure 4, the squares of order 108 is given by

17.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316	337	358
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317	338	359
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318	339	360
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319	340	361
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320	341	362
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321	342	363
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322	343	364
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323	344	365
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324	345	366
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325	346	367
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326	347	368
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327	348	369
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328	349	370
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329	350	371
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330	351	372
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331	352	373
17	38	59	80	101	122	143	164	185	206	227	248	269	290	311	332	353	374
18	39	60	81	102	123	144	165	186	207	228	249	270	291	312	333	354	375

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{108 \times 108} := 53999999999999946$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 2999999999999997$.

3.1.11 Order 114

According to Figure 4, the squares of order 114 is given by

18.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316	337	358	379
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317	338	359	380
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318	339	360	381
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319	340	361	382
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320	341	362	383
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321	342	363	384
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322	343	364	385
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323	344	365	386
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324	345	366	387
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325	346	367	388
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326	347	368	389
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327	348	369	390
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328	349	370	391
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329	350	371	392
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330	351	372	393
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331	352	373	394
17	38	59	80	101	122	143	164	185	206	227	248	269	290	311	332	353	374	395
18	39	60	81	102	123	144	165	186	207	228	249	270	291	312	333	354	375	396
19	40	61	82	103	124	145	166	187	208	229	250	271	292	313	334	355	376	397

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{114 \times 114} := 5699999999999943$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 2999999999999997$.

3.1.12 Order 120

According to Figure 4, the square of order 120 is given by

19.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316	337	358	379	400
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317	338	359	380	401
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318	339	360	381	402
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319	340	361	382	403
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320	341	362	383	404
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321	342	363	384	405
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322	343	364	385	406
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323	344	365	386	407
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324	345	366	387	408
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325	346	367	388	409
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326	347	368	389	410
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327	348	369	390	411
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328	349	370	391	412
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329	350	371	392	413
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330	351	372	393	414
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331	352	373	394	415
17	38	59	80	101	122	143	164	185	206	227	248	269	290	311	332	353	374	395	416
18	39	60	81	102	123	144	165	186	207	228	249	270	291	312	333	354	375	396	417
19	40	61	82	103	124	145	166	187	208	229	250	271	292	313	334	355	376	397	418
20	41	62	83	104	125	146	167	188	209	230	251	272	293	314	335	356	377	398	419

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{120 \times 120} := 5999999999999940$. All the 6×6 blocks are **universal** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums, $S_{6 \times 6} = 2999999999999997$.

Remark 3.1. In case of *universal pandiagonal* magic square of order 128, we applied three different ways to write *universal pandiagonal* magic squares multiples of 4 and 8. In the case of order 126, the other ways can also be applied easily. See the following three figures.

Figure 5.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316	337	358	379	400	421
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317	338	359	380	401	422
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318	339	360	381	402	423
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319	340	361	382	403	424
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320	341	362	383	404	425
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321	342	363	384	405	426
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322	343	364	385	406	427
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323	344	365	386	407	428
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324	345	366	387	408	429
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325	346	367	388	409	430
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326	347	368	389	410	431
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327	348	369	390	411	432
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328	349	370	391	412	433
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329	350	371	392	413	434
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330	351	372	393	414	435
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331	352	373	394	415	436
17	38	59	80	101	122	143	164	185	206	227	248	269	290	311	332	353	374	395	416	437
18	39	60	81	102	123	144	165	186	207	228	249	270	291	312	333	354	375	396	417	438
19	40	61	82	103	124	145	166	187	208	229	250	271	292	313	334	355	376	397	418	439
20	41	62	83	104	125	146	167	188	209	230	251	272	293	314	335	356	377	398	419	440
21	42	63	84	105	126	147	168	189	210	231	252	273	294	315	336	357	378	399	420	441

Figure 6.

1	21	41	61	81	101	121	141	161	181	201	221	241	261	281	301	321	341	361	381
2	22	42	62	82	102	122	142	162	182	202	222	242	262	282	302	322	342	362	382
3	23	43	63	83	103	123	143	163	183	203	223	243	263	283	303	323	343	363	383
4	24	44	64	84	104	124	144	164	184	204	224	244	264	284	304	324	344	364	384
5	25	45	65	85	105	125	145	165	185	205	225	245	265	285	305	325	345	365	385
6	26	46	66	86	106	126	146	166	186	206	226	246	266	286	306	326	346	366	386
7	27	47	67	87	107	127	147	167	187	207	227	247	267	287	307	327	347	367	387
8	28	48	68	88	108	128	148	168	188	208	228	248	268	288	308	328	348	368	388
9	29	49	69	89	109	129	149	169	189	209	229	249	269	289	309	329	349	369	389
10	30	50	70	90	110	130	150	170	190	210	230	250	270	290	310	330	350	370	390
11	31	51	71	91	111	131	151	171	191	211	231	251	271	291	311	331	351	371	391
12	32	52	72	92	112	132	152	172	192	212	232	252	272	292	312	332	352	372	392
13	33	53	73	93	113	133	153	173	193	213	233	253	273	293	313	333	353	373	393
14	34	54	74	94	114	134	154	174	194	214	234	254	274	294	314	334	354	374	394
15	35	55	75	95	115	135	155	175	195	215	235	255	275	295	315	335	355	375	395
16	36	56	76	96	116	136	156	176	196	216	236	256	276	296	316	336	356	376	396
17	37	57	77	97	117	137	157	177	197	217	237	257	277	297	317	337	357	377	397
18	38	58	78	98	118	138	158	178	198	218	238	258	278	298	318	338	358	378	398
19	39	59	79	99	119	139	159	179	199	219	239	259	279	299	319	339	359	379	399
20	40	60	80	100	120	140	160	180	200	220	240	260	280	300	320	340	360	380	400

Figure 7.

1	22	43	64	85	106	127	148	169	190	211	232	253	274	295	316	337	358	379	400	421
2	23	44	65	86	107	128	149	170	191	212	233	254	275	296	317	338	359	380	401	422
3	24	45	66	87	108	129	150	171	192	213	234	255	276	297	318	339	360	381	402	423
4	25	46	67	88	109	130	151	172	193	214	235	256	277	298	319	340	361	382	403	424
5	26	47	68	89	110	131	152	173	194	215	236	257	278	299	320	341	362	383	404	425
6	27	48	69	90	111	132	153	174	195	216	237	258	279	300	321	342	363	384	405	426
7	28	49	70	91	112	133	154	175	196	217	238	259	280	301	322	343	364	385	406	427
8	29	50	71	92	113	134	155	176	197	218	239	260	281	302	323	344	365	386	407	428
9	30	51	72	93	114	135	156	177	198	219	240	261	282	303	324	345	366	387	408	429
10	31	52	73	94	115	136	157	178	199	220	241	262	283	304	325	346	367	388	409	430
11	32	53	74	95	116	137	158	179	200	221	242	263	284	305	326	347	368	389	410	431
12	33	54	75	96	117	138	159	180	201	222	243	264	285	306	327	348	369	390	411	432
13	34	55	76	97	118	139	160	181	202	223	244	265	286	307	328	349	370	391	412	433
14	35	56	77	98	119	140	161	182	203	224	245	266	287	308	329	350	371	392	413	434
15	36	57	78	99	120	141	162	183	204	225	246	267	288	309	330	351	372	393	414	435
16	37	58	79	100	121	142	163	184	205	226	247	268	289	310	331	352	373	394	415	436
17	38	59	80	101	122	143	164	185	206	227	248	269	290	311	332	353	374	395	416	437
18	39	60	81	102	123	144	165	186	207	228	249	270	291	312	333	354	375	396	417	438
19	40	61	82	103	124	145	166	187	208	229	250	271	292	313	334	355	376	397	418	439
20	41	62	83	104	125	146	167	188	209	230	251	272	293	314	335	356	377	398	419	440
21	42	63	84	105	126	147	168	189	210	231	252	273	294	315	336	357	378	399	420	441

4 Universal Magic Square of Order 120

Let's write the Table 9 in a simplified way.

one is multiple of order 3. In this case, it is **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 given in Example 8, where blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares of order 3 with **different semi-magic sums**.

The Table 14 represents **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 120 with **magic sum**: $S_{120 \times 120} := 5999999999999940$. Each number represent a **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 with equal **magic sum**: $S_{12 \times 12} := 599999999999994$. Moreover, the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares with **different semi-magic sums**. These **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 12 are given in Appendix 7. Below are the magic sums of **universal pandiagonal** magic squares multiples of 12.

Table 15. Below are magic sums of magic squares multiples of 12 up to order 120.

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{12 \times 12} &:= 599999999999994 \times 1 = 599999999999994 \\
 S_{24 \times 24} &:= 599999999999994 \times 2 = 1199999999999988 \\
 S_{36 \times 36} &:= 599999999999994 \times 3 = 1799999999999982 \\
 S_{48 \times 48} &:= 599999999999994 \times 4 = 2399999999999976 \\
 S_{60 \times 60} &:= 599999999999994 \times 5 = 2999999999999970
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{72 \times 72} &:= 599999999999994 \times 6 = 3599999999999964 \\
 S_{84 \times 84} &:= 599999999999994 \times 7 = 4199999999999958 \\
 S_{96 \times 96} &:= 599999999999994 \times 8 = 4799999999999952 \\
 S_{108 \times 108} &:= 599999999999994 \times 9 = 5399999999999946 \\
 S_{120 \times 120} &:= 599999999999994 \times 10 = 5999999999999940
 \end{aligned}$$

4.1 Universal Pandiagonal Magic Squares Multiples of 12

In this case we shall bring **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of orders multiples of 12 up to order 108. The **universal pandiagonal** magic square of order 120 is already given in 14. The following procedure shall be used to write **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of multiples of 12.

Figure 8.

1	11	21	31	41	51	61	71	81	91
2	12	22	32	42	52	62	72	82	92
3	13	23	33	43	53	63	73	83	93
4	14	24	34	44	54	64	74	84	94
5	15	25	35	45	55	65	75	85	95
6	16	26	36	46	56	66	76	86	96
7	17	27	37	47	57	67	77	87	97
8	18	28	38	48	58	68	78	88	98
9	19	29	39	49	59	69	79	89	99
10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100

4.1.1 Orders 24, 36, 48 and 60

According to Figure 8, the magic squares of orders 24, 36, 48 and 60 are given by

1.

1	11
2	12

2.

1	11	21
2	12	22
3	13	23

3.

1	11	21	31
2	12	22	32
3	13	23	33
4	14	24	34

4.

1	11	21	31	41
2	12	22	32	42
3	13	23	33	43
4	14	24	34	44
5	15	25	35	45

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{24 \times 24} := 1199999999999988$, $S_{36 \times 36} := 1799999999999982$, $S_{48 \times 48} := 2399999999999976$ and $S_{60 \times 60} = 5999999999999940$. The magic squares of orders 24, 36, 48 and 60 are **universal pandiagonal**. All the 12×12 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 12 with equal magic sums, $S_{12 \times 12} = 599999999999994$.

4.1.2 Orders 72 and 84

According to Figure 8, the magic squares of orders 72 and 84 are given by

5.

1	11	21	31	41	51
2	12	22	32	42	52
3	13	23	33	43	53
4	14	24	34	44	54
5	15	25	35	45	55
6	16	26	36	46	56

6.

1	11	21	31	41	51	61
2	12	22	32	42	52	62
3	13	23	33	43	53	63
4	14	24	34	44	54	64
5	15	25	35	45	55	65
6	16	26	36	46	56	66
7	17	27	37	47	57	67

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{72 \times 72} := 3599999999999964$ and $S_{84 \times 84} = 4199999999999958$. The magic squares of orders 72 and 84 are **universal pandiagonal**. All the 12×12 blocks are **universal pandiagonal** magic squares of order 12 with equal magic sums, $S_{12 \times 12} = 599999999999994$.

4.1.3 Order 96 and 108

According to Figure 8, the magic squares of orders 96 and 108 are given by

7.

1	11	21	31	41	51	61	71
2	12	22	32	42	52	62	72
3	13	23	33	43	53	63	73
4	14	24	34	44	54	64	74
5	15	25	35	45	55	65	75
6	16	26	36	46	56	66	76
7	17	27	37	47	57	67	77
8	18	28	38	48	58	68	78

8.

1	11	21	31	41	51	61	71	81
2	12	22	32	42	52	62	72	82
3	13	23	33	43	53	63	73	83
4	14	24	34	44	54	64	74	84
5	15	25	35	45	55	65	75	85
6	16	26	36	46	56	66	76	86
7	17	27	37	47	57	67	77	87
8	18	28	38	48	58	68	78	88
9	19	29	39	49	59	69	79	89

In this case, the magic sums are $S_{96 \times 96} := 4799999999999952$ and $S_{108 \times 108} = 4199999999999958$. The magic squares of orders 96 and 108 are **universal pandiagonal**. All the 12×12 blocks are **universal**

86.	1818881881811	181818181188	188118181888	8181881881811	8118881181818	8181188818181	18881818118188	1881818181881	1888188818181	8118818818811	8118181818818	8118181818181
	1881181818188	1818881818188	1818188818181	8118881881811	8181818188181	8181881181818	18818188818181	18881881181881	1888181181881	8118181188188	811881818181	8111818881881
	1818181818188	1881188818181	1818881181888	8181181818181	8181881881818	8118881881811	18881818181881	18881818818181	1888188118188	8118188181811	8118181881881	8118811881888
	8181188818181	8118881181881	8181881818188	1881188181811	1818181818818	18188818818811	8118181818188	8118181818188	8118881881811	1888188818118	1881818181818	1888181881811
	8181881181881	818118818188	81188818818181	1818188818811	1818881818181	1881181881888	8118188818181	8118881818188	8181818181818	1888181181818	1888181881811	1881888181818
	8118881818188	81818818818181	818118181881	1818881188188	1881188818811	1818188181811	8118881181818	8118181881811	8118181818188	1881818188181	1888181881818	1888181818188
	81118181881811	8118181881818	8118811818181	1888181818188	1888181881811	1881818181818	8181118188188	8181881881811	8118881818181	181818818188	1881188818181	1818881181881
	8118181181818	811881881811	8118188818181	1881818881811	1888181818188	1888181181818	8118881881811	8181188181811	8181881188188	188118181881	1818881818188	1818188818181
	8118818818181	8118181818181	8118181881811	1888181818188	1888181818188	1888188818111	8181881818181	8118881181818	8181188818811	18188818818181	181818181881	1881188181888
	1881818818181	18881818818811	1888181818818	811881181881	81181818818181	8118188181818	1818881181818	1881188818118	1818181881811	8118881818188	8181881881811	8181181818188
	1888181188188	1888188181811	18818188818811	8118188818181	8118818181888	8118181181881	1818188818188	1818881881811	188118181818	818188118188	818118181888	8118881881811
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8 Author’s Contributions to Magic Squares

The item-wise author’s work on magic squares is as follows:

1. *Digital Numbers Magic Squares - [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 37];*
2. *Block-Wise Construction of Bimagic Squares - [11];*
3. *Connections with Genetic Tables and Shannon’s entropy - [12];*
4. *Selfie and Palindromic-type Magic Squares - [13, 28, 37];*
5. *Intervally Distributed and Block-Wise Magic Squares - [14, 15, 16, 28];*
6. *Multi-digits and Number Patterns Magic Squares - [17, 27];*

7. *Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares with Uniformity, Minimum Sum and Pythagorean Triples - [18, 19];*
8. *Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares - [20, 21, 22, 23, 26, 29, 31];*
9. *Magic Crosses: Repeated and Non Repeated Entries - [24];*
10. *Representations of Letters and Numbers With Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 6 - [25].*
11. *Bordered Magic Squares - [32, 33, 34, 35, 36].*
12. *Block-Bordered Magic Squares - [45, 46, 47].*
13. *2-Digits Magic and Bimagic Squares - [38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44].*

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